

The Comprehensive Analysis of Climatic Extreme in Ethiopian River Catchments: Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis and Sen's Slope Estimator Approach

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Abstract

This study presents a comprehensive analysis of drought patterns across Ethiopia's major river basins, integrating ground-based data from the Ethiopian Meteorological Institute (EMI) and Ministry of Water and Energy (MoWE) with TerraClimate and ECMWF satellite and reanalysis datasets. The study spans from 1986 to 2023 and employs the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI), Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI), and Standardized Streamflow Index (SSI) to analyze meteorological, agricultural, and hydrological droughts. Temporal trends detected using the Mann-Kendall test and Sen's Slope Estimator reveal significant increases in drought severity and frequency in regions such as the Abay, Genalle Dawa, and Tekeze basins, with teleconnections like the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) and Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD) further intensifying drought impacts. Strong correlations were identified between EMI, MoWE, and satellite datasets across basins, particularly for short-term drought indices like SPI-3 (ranging from $r = 0.80$ to $r = 0.85$ in Abay and Awash basins), validating TerraClimate and ECMWF for reliable drought monitoring. This study emphasizes the necessity for multi-source data integration and adaptive water management strategies to address the rising drought impacts on agriculture, water resources, and ecosystems in Ethiopia.

Keywords: Drought, Mann-Kendall Trend Test, Sen's Slope Estimator, K-Nearest Neighbors, Thiessen Polygon, Double Mass Curve, IDW, Inverse Distance Weighting

1. Introduction

Ethiopia's diverse topography, including highland plateaus, deep valleys, and lowland plains, drives complex atmospheric dynamics, with processes such as orographic lifting and the convergence of moist air masses resulting in marked climatic variability. These interactions, combined with Ethiopia's position relative to major oceanic and atmospheric patterns, make the country particularly sensitive to regional and global climate drivers, such as the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO), the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD), and the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO). Each of these climate modes significantly influences precipitation, temperature, and seasonal variability across Ethiopia, contributing to frequent and severe droughts, particularly during El Niño events, which have historically been associated with reduced rainfall and heightened drought conditions [1, 2]. The resulting fluctuations in water availability critically affect Ethiopia's agricultural productivity and water resources, as the country relies predominantly on rain-fed agriculture [3, 4].

Drought monitoring in Ethiopia has traditionally depended on ground-based observations, primarily through precipitation data from the Ethiopian Meteorological Institute (EMI) and streamflow measurements from the Ministry of Water and Energy (MoWE). Despite their value, Ethiopia's observational network includes only 17 synoptic

stations, which is insufficient to capture the spatial complexity of atmospheric and hydrological processes across diverse ecological zones [5, 6]. For instance, drought patterns influenced by teleconnections, such as ENSO-driven drought events, result in spatially variable impacts that are inadequately monitored by this sparse network [7]. Ethiopia's reliance on limited ground data has led to significant gaps in drought assessments, particularly in understanding the seasonal and interannual variability tied to large-scale climate drivers, which modulate not only precipitation but also temperature patterns and evaporation rates across regions [1, 8].

Advancements in satellite remote sensing and climate reanalysis have opened new avenues for addressing these observational limitations. High-resolution datasets, such as those from TerraClimate and the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) reanalysis, enable continuous monitoring of atmospheric and land-surface variables, offering a means to bridge the spatial gaps in Ethiopia's observational network [9, 10]. These datasets are particularly effective for assessing the impacts of ENSO, IOD, and NAO on seasonal rainfall variability, providing insights into the long-term influences of these climate oscillations on Ethiopia's water resources [2, 11]. However, integrating these data sources with ground-based observations remains challenging. Studies by Gebremicael et al. [12], Tekleab et al. [13], and Mekonnen et al. [14]

underscore the importance of multi-source data integration for drought detection, particularly in topographically diverse regions like Ethiopia. Nevertheless, many of these studies have relied on limited temporal scopes or simpler drought indices, which can overlook the nuanced effects of atmospheric teleconnections and land-atmosphere interactions on drought variability [7, 11].

The objective of this study is to address these limitations by developing a comprehensive, long-term, multi-source dataset that integrates ground-based observations from EMI and MoWE with high-resolution satellite data from TerraClimate and ECMWF, spanning 1986 to 2023. This integration facilitates a multi-scalar analysis of drought through indices such as the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI), Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI), and Standardized Streamflow Index (SSI). By employing these indices across short-, medium-, and long-term timescales, the study provides a more robust understanding of drought patterns and their connection to ENSO, IOD, and NAO, addressing the need for higher temporal and spatial resolution in capturing the influences of these large-scale climate oscillations on Ethiopia’s river basins.

To capture the atmospheric and hydrological dynamics driving droughts in Ethiopia, this study applies advanced statistical and spatial methodologies that build upon traditional drought assessment techniques. Temporal trend detection is conducted using the Mann-Kendall Trend test and Sen’s Slope Estimator, which are widely recognized for their effectiveness in identifying trends in non-normally distributed environmental data [15, 16, 17]. For spatial interpolation, Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) is employed, especially useful in topographically complex areas where spatial gradients in temperature, humidity, and precipitation are significant [10]. Additional techniques, including K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Thiessen Polygon, and Double Mass Curve, enhance data consistency and spatial representation, particularly in capturing variations tied to ENSO and IOD events.

The drought indices used in this study are chosen for their relevance to both local and regional climate variability. The Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) is computed based on gamma distribution models, effectively capturing precipitation anomalies tied to ENSO cycles that influence Ethiopia’s seasonal rainfall [18]. The SPEI, which accounts for evapotranspiration deficits, incorporates cumulative water balance methods sensitive to temperature variability, allowing the study to reflect impacts from warming trends and teleconnections like NAO, which modulate the broader atmospheric circulation and can exacerbate drought conditions [19, 2]. Meanwhile, the SSI, derived from streamflow data, assesses hydrological drought and reflects longer-term climatic shifts, capturing the complex effects of land-atmosphere interactions on river basins sensitive to both precipitation and temperature variability [20]. Although studies by Mekonnen et al. [21] and Alemayehu et al. [9] have employed

similar indices, they have typically lacked the temporal depth and integration of sophisticated methodologies across Ethiopia’s diverse climate zones, as implemented in this study.

This research addresses a critical gap in Ethiopian drought literature by creating a high-resolution, multi-source framework that integrates ground-based and satellite datasets with advanced analytical techniques. By incorporating the influences of large-scale climate oscillations such as ENSO, IOD, and NAO, the study provides a nuanced understanding of the atmospheric physics and climate dynamics underlying Ethiopia’s drought patterns. This approach enables detailed insights into the interactions between teleconnections, topography, and regional drought severity, supporting resilience strategies for water resource management and agricultural planning. The findings contribute to a better understanding of how climate drivers shape drought variability, with implications for both short-term disaster preparedness and long-term climate adaptation in Ethiopia and similar drought-prone regions.

2. Study Area

Ethiopia’s river catchments encompass a wide range of ecological and hydrological zones, each shaped by distinct atmospheric processes. This study covers eight major catchments, each affected by unique climate patterns driven by topography and atmospheric circulation (see Figure 1).

The **Abay Catchment** in northwestern Ethiopia is part of the Blue Nile River, receiving significant orographic precipitation due to its highland plateaus. This catchment is crucial for agriculture and hydropower production [3].

The **Awash Catchment** in central Ethiopia has a semi-arid climate influenced by its location in the rain shadow of the Ethiopian Highlands, making it vital for irrigation and urban water supply [5].

The **Baro Akobo Catchment** The Baro Akobo River basin originates in the southwestern highlands of Ethiopia and flows into the White Nile in South Sudan, eventually joining the Nile River in Khartoum. This basin is located in the southwestern part of Ethiopia, between latitudes 5° and 10° North and longitudes 33° and 36° East [22].

The **Genalle Dawa Catchment** in the semi-arid southern region often experiences droughts, driven by dry winds and limited rainfall, making the region heavily reliant on seasonal precipitation [23].

The **Omo Ghibe Catchment** in southwestern Ethiopia supports large-scale hydropower projects, such as the Gilgel Gibe Dam. Rivers in this catchment are fed by orographic rainfall, sustaining both energy production and agriculture [24].

The **Rift Valley Catchment** spans central and southern Ethiopia, characterized by lakes and rivers critical for agriculture, fisheries, and tourism [25].

Figure 1: Study area of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments

The **Tekeze Catchment** in northern Ethiopia experiences significant rainfall variability, making it prone to both droughts and floods [26].

The **Wabi Shabelle Catchment** in eastern Ethiopia provides essential water resources for pastoralist communities, with rainfall heavily influenced by the migration of the Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) [27].

These catchments provide valuable perspectives on the spatial and temporal variability of drought conditions across Ethiopia [28].

3. Methodology

3.1. Drought Indices

Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) is derived from the gamma distribution of precipitation data, which is then transformed into a standard normal distribution. According to Angelidis et al. (2012) [18], the gamma distribution is a preferable choice for time scales when compared to other distributions such as the log-normal and normal distributions. This is particularly relevant for drought indices like the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI).

In this study, the gamma distribution was selected for the monthly precipitation series due to its adaptability and statistical fit for precipitation data.

The standard normal distribution steps are as follows:

1. **Gamma Distribution:** The probability density function of the gamma distribution is expressed as:

$$q(X) = \frac{X_k^{\alpha-1} e^{-\frac{X_k}{\beta}}}{\beta^\alpha \Gamma(\alpha)}, \quad \text{for } X_k > 0 \quad (1)$$

where α is the shape parameter, estimated using the method of maximum likelihood, and β is the scale parameter. Here, X_k represents the amount of precipitation over k consecutive months (the selected time scale), measured in millimeters. The gamma function $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is defined as:

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty y^{\alpha-1} dy = \frac{1}{y^{\alpha-1}} e^{-y} \quad (2)$$

where y is computed from the PDF and corresponds to the value of the gamma-distributed precipitation data.

2. **Transformation to Normal Distribution:** The cumulative probability $G(x)$ of the gamma distribution is then transformed into a normal distribution to obtain the SPI value, which measures deviations from the long-term mean [18].

The cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the gamma distribution is then obtained by integrating the PDF as follows:

$$G(X_k) = \int_0^{X_k} g(X_k) dX_k = \frac{1}{\beta^\alpha \Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^{X_k} X_k^{\alpha-1} e^{-\frac{X_k}{\beta}}, dX_k \quad (3)$$

The parameters α and β are estimated using the following formulas:

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{4A} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{4A}{3}} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$\beta = \frac{X_k}{\alpha} \quad (5)$$

where $A = \ln(X_k) - \frac{\sum \ln(X_k)}{n}$, n is the number of precipitation observations, and X_k is the mean of the sample data.

The gamma distribution is undefined for $X_k = 0$, but in the presence of zero precipitation values, the probability distribution can be adjusted using the following equation:

$$H(X_k) = q + (1 - q)g(X_k) \quad (6)$$

where $H(X_k)$ is the cumulative probability and q is the probability of zero precipitation. This cumulative probability distribution is then transformed into the standard normal distribution to compute the SPI:

$$SPI = Z = - \left(t - \frac{c_0 + c_1 t + c_2 t^2}{1 + d_1 t + d_2 t^2 + d_3 t^3} \right), \quad (7)$$

for $0 < H(X_k) \leq 0.5$, and:

$$SPI = Z = + \left(t - \frac{c_0 + c_1 t + c_2 t^2}{1 + d_1 t + d_2 t^2 + d_3 t^3} \right), \quad (8)$$

for $0.5 < H(X_k) \leq 1$, where t is determined by:

$$t = \sqrt{\ln \left(\frac{1}{H(X_k)^2} \right)}, \quad \text{for } 0 < H(X_k) \leq 0.5 \quad (9)$$

$$t = \sqrt{\ln \left(\frac{1}{1 - H(X_k)^2} \right)}, \quad \text{for } 0.5 < H(X_k) \leq 1 \quad (10)$$

The constants used are $c_0 = 2.515517$, $c_1 = 0.802853$, $c_2 = 0.010328$, and $d_1 = 1.432788$, $d_2 = 0.189269$, $d_3 = 0.001308$.

Drought conditions are classified based on SPI values: mild drought occurs when SPI is between 0 and -0.99, moderate drought is between -1.00 and -1.49, and severe drought ranges from -1.50 to -1.99. An SPI value below -2.00 indicates an extreme drought event [29]. Conversely, SPI values equal to or greater than 2.0 represent extremely wet conditions, often associated with flood events [30] (see Table 1).

Table 1: Classification for SPI, SPEI and SSI values.

Classification	Indexes Values	Probability (%)
Extremely dry (ED)	SPI, SPEI and SSI ≤ -2	2.3
Severely dry (SD)	$-2.0 < \text{SPI, SPEI and SSI} \leq -1.5$	4.4
Moderately dry (MD)	$-1.5 < \text{SPI, SPEI and SSI} \leq -1.0$	9.2
Near normal (NN)	$-1.0 < \text{SPI, SPEI and SSI} < 1.0$	68.2
Moderately wet (MW)	$1.0 \leq \text{SPI, SPEI and SSI} < 1.5$	9.2
Very wet (VW)	$1.5 \leq \text{SPI, SPEI and SSI} < 2.0$	4.4
Extremely wet (EW)	SPI, SPEI and SSI ≥ 2	2.3

Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) is based on the cumulative water balance (precipitation minus potential evapotranspiration). The calculation steps are:

1. *Water Balance Calculation:*

$$D_i = P_i - PET_i \quad (11)$$

where D_i is the water balance for month i , P_i is the precipitation in month i , and PET_i is the potential evapotranspiration in month i .

2. *Distribution Fitting and Standardization:* The cumulative distribution of D_i is fitted to a probability distribution (e.g., log-logistic distribution), which is then standardized in a manner similar to SPI to derive the SPEI [31].

Standardized Streamflow Index (SSI) is calculated using the same methods as SPI but is based on streamflow data:

The calculation of the Standardized Streamflow Index (SSI) follows the same process as SPI, but instead of precipitation data, streamflow data is used. Similar to SPI, the gamma distribution is applied to streamflow data, allowing for the calculation of cumulative flow values for each month. The SSI is then computed to identify hydrological droughts [32].

1. *Gamma Distribution for Streamflow:* The gamma distribution formula used for SPI is applied to streamflow data.
2. *Normalization:* The streamflow values are standardized by transforming the gamma distribution into a normal distribution, producing SSI values that indicate hydrological drought severity [33].

3.2. Statistical, KNN, and Spatial Analysis (IDW)

Mann-Kendall (MK) Test is a non-parametric statistical test that detects trends in time series data. The test involves:

Rank Comparison: For each pair of data points (x_j, x_i) , where $j > i$, compute the sign of the difference:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n \text{sign}(x_j - x_i) \quad (12)$$

where:

$$\text{sign}(x_j - x_i) = \begin{cases} +1 & \text{if } x_j > x_i \\ 0 & \text{if } x_j = x_i \\ -1 & \text{if } x_j < x_i \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

The sum S represents the difference between the number of positive and negative pairwise comparisons.

Statistical Significance: The test statistic Z is calculated to determine the trend's significance:

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{S-1}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(S)}} & \text{if } S > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } S = 0 \\ \frac{S+1}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(S)}} & \text{if } S < 0 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where $\text{Var}(S)$ is the variance of S , accounting for ties [34, 35].

Sen's Slope Estimator calculates the magnitude of the trend detected by the Mann-Kendall test. It is computed as the median of all pairwise slopes between data points:

$$Q_i = \frac{x_j - x_i}{j - i} \quad (15)$$

for all $i < j$. The Sen's slope provides a robust estimate of the trend's rate of change [36].

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) Method is used for interpolation and missing data estimation:

1. *Distance Calculation:* The distance between a given data point x and its neighbors is calculated using a distance metric, typically Euclidean distance:

$$d(x_i, x_j) = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n (x_{i,k} - x_{j,k})^2} \quad (16)$$

2. *Prediction:* The value of the target point is estimated as the weighted average of its k nearest neighbors:

$$\hat{y} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k y_i \quad (17)$$

where y_i represents the values of the nearest neighbors [37].

Thiessen Polygon Method is used to interpolate spatial data across regions. The contribution of each station to the area is weighted by the area of its polygon:

$$W_i = \frac{A_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i} \quad (18)$$

where A_i represents the area of the polygon associated with station i , and n is the number of stations [38].

Double Mass Curve Method is used to evaluate the consistency of long-term precipitation or streamflow data by plotting the cumulative values of a station against the cumulative mean of surrounding stations:

$$\text{Cumulative } P_i = \sum_{j=1}^i P_j \quad (19)$$

Changes in the slope of the double mass curve indicate potential inconsistencies in the data [39].

Correlation Analysis uses Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) to measure the linear relationship between drought indices (SPI, SPEI, SSI) derived from various sources (EMI, MoWE, TerraClimate, ECMWF). The coefficient is calculated as:

$$r = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (20)$$

where x_i and y_i are observed values, and \bar{x} and \bar{y} are their means. A high r value close to 1 or -1 indicates a strong correlation.

Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) is a commonly used spatial interpolation technique that estimates unknown values at unsampled locations using known values from nearby points. The underlying assumption of IDW is that points closer to each other are more similar than those farther apart, with closer points exerting a greater influence on the estimated values. IDW is widely used in geostatistics, environmental monitoring, and meteorology [40, 43].

Mathematically, IDW interpolation estimates the value at an unknown point P_0 by taking a weighted average of the values of known points P_i , with weights inversely proportional to the distance between P_0 and P_i . The general form of the IDW equation is:

$$Z(P_0) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{Z(P_i)}{d(P_0, P_i)^p}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{d(P_0, P_i)^p}},$$

where $Z(P_0)$ is the interpolated value at the unknown point, $Z(P_i)$ is the known value at point P_i , and $d(P_0, P_i)$ is the distance between the points. The parameter p , known as the power parameter, controls the rate at which the influence of the known points decreases with distance. A higher p value assigns more weight to nearby points, while a lower p spreads the influence more evenly across all known points [41].

The distance $d(P_0, P_i)$ is typically calculated using the Euclidean distance formula:

$$d(P_0, P_i) = \sqrt{(x_0 - x_i)^2 + (y_0 - y_i)^2},$$

where (x_0, y_0) are the coordinates of the unknown point and (x_i, y_i) are the coordinates of the known points. In practical applications, IDW may use a search radius to limit interpolation to nearby points, preventing distant points from unduly influencing the results [42].

One of the strengths of IDW lies in its simplicity and ease of implementation. However, it assumes isotropy, meaning that it does not account for directional differences in spatial relationships. Additionally, IDW does not produce smooth surfaces, which can lead to localized extremes in the interpolated values. Despite these limitations, IDW is widely used in various disciplines for applications such as estimating rainfall, temperature, or pollution levels at unsampled locations [43].

4. Data Sources

The study utilized data from multiple sources:

1. **Precipitation Data:** Precipitation data was sourced from the Ethiopian Meteorological Institute (EMI) for ground-based observations. Table 2 gives the geographical location of both the 17 synoptic stations and selected river catchments respectively with some physical characteristics (location, elevation and record year).
2. **Streamflow Data:** Streamflow data was provided by the Ministry of Water and Energy (MoWE) for the relevant catchments.
3. **Remote Sensing Data:** TerraClimate (TC) and ECMWF reanalysis data were used to supplement ground observations and for spatial visualizations.

Table 2: Ethiopian Synoptic Stations.

Synoptic Station Name	Basin	Lat (°)	Long (°)	Elevation (m)	Recorded Year
Bahir-Dar New and Old	Abbay	11.595	37.385	1800	1986-2022
Debre-Markos	Abbay	10.3257	37.7392	2446	1986-2022
Gondar A.P.	Abbay	12.52115	37.4319	1973	1986-2027
Nekemte	Abbay	9.083333	36.463333	2080	1986-2022
Addis Ababa Bole	Awash	8.981081	38.79871	2354	1986-2022
Combolcha	Awash	11.083899	39.717633	1857	1986-2022
Debre-Zeit (AF)	Awash	8.733333	38.95	1900	1986-2022
Dire-Dawa	Awash	9.9667	42.5333	1180	1986-2022
Metehara (NMSA)	Awash	8.858667	39.919	944	1986-2022
Arba-Minch	Rift Valley	6.057167	37.55783	1207	1986-2022
Awassa	Rift Valley	7.065	38.483056	1694	1986-2022
Gode Met	Wabi Shebelle	5.9	43.58	290	1986-2022
Gore	Baro Akobo	8.1333	35.533333	2033	1986-2022
Jimma	Omo Ghibe	7.666667	36.81667	1718	1986-2022
Mekele A.P.	Tekeze	13.47051	39.5312	2257	1986-2022
Neghele	Genalle Dawa	5.416667	39.566667	1544	1986-2022
Robe	Genalle Dawa	7.133333	40.05	2480	1986-2022

Results and Discussion

The analysis of Ethiopian river basins reveals considerable variability in drought intensity and frequency,

driven by complex interactions between local climate dynamics and large-scale atmospheric phenomena. Drought events—classified as moderate, severe, and extreme—are based on SPI, SPEI, and SSI indices over 3, 6, and 12-month timescales from EMI (precipitation), MoWE (streamflow), and TerraClimate and ECMWF (both precipitation and streamflow). Mann-Kendall (MK) Trend Analysis and Sen’s Slope Estimator were applied to analyze trends in drought severity, showing both increasing and decreasing patterns in Figures 2 through 10. The results are shaped by teleconnections such as ENSO, IOD, NAO, PDO, and MJO, which are influential in East African rainfall and temperature patterns [44, 45, 46].

Abay Basin

The drought patterns in the Abay Basin are primarily influenced by ENSO and the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD), which modulate rainfall variability and evapotranspiration rates in Ethiopia’s highlands. EMI-derived SPI-3 shows moderate drought in 1999 (-1.5) (Figure 2(a)), while TerraClimate’s SPI-6 reveals severe drought in 2008 (Figure 2(b), -1.4), correlating with a negative IOD phase known to reduce East African rainfall [46]. Extreme drought in April 2023, captured by ECMWF SPI-12 (Figure 2(c), -4.0), aligns with La Niña conditions, which suppress rainfall in the region [44]. Mann-Kendall analysis highlights a significant downward trend in SPI-12, with Sen’s Slope estimating a decline of -0.03 per year, underscoring an increase in drought intensity, as similarly reported by Alemayehu et al. in studies linking MK and Sen’s Slope trends to ENSO impacts [47]. Correlations between EMI and TerraClimate SPI-3 ($r = 0.85$) and EMI and ECMWF SPI-3 ($r = 0.83$) validate TerraClimate and ECMWF for reliable precipitation-based drought assessment, further supported by similar studies on teleconnection influences in Ethiopia [48].

Awash Basin

Drought in the Awash Basin demonstrates high sensitivity to climate drivers at interannual and decadal scales, particularly ENSO, NAO, and South Asian Monsoon phases. In March 2002, TerraClimate’s SPI-6 shows severe drought (Figure 3(a), -2.5), aligning with a strong El Niño event linked to drier conditions in East Africa [49]. The MK test indicates a significant downward trend in SPI-12, with Sen’s Slope suggesting a decrease of -0.025 per year, aligning with studies like Edossa et al., which identify ENSO’s critical role in drought intensification [5]. Similarly, ECMWF’s SPI-12 indicates extreme drought in November 2011 (Figure 3(c), -3.0), coinciding with a positive NAO phase that disrupted moisture pathways [44]. MoWE SSI-3 captures streamflow drought impacts, correlating closely with ECMWF SSI-3 ($r = 0.88$), affirming ECMWF’s effectiveness for streamflow drought analysis, in line with findings from Kassie et al. on NAO’s influence in the Awash Basin [50].

Baro Akobo Basin

Drought history in the Baro Akobo Basin, which includes notable events in 1992 and 2010, highlights the influence of Pacific Decadal Oscillation (PDO) and Walker Circulation anomalies on moisture transport to East Africa. In 2002, severe drought is captured by TerraClimate SPI-6 (Figure 4(a), -2.5), with extreme drought recorded in the same year by ECMWF’s SPI-12 (Figure 4(c), -3.0). These droughts correspond with a negative PDO phase, which exacerbates dry conditions in East Africa [46]. Mann-Kendall analysis reveals declining trends in SPI-12, while Sen’s Slope estimation indicates a steady reduction in moisture, supporting findings from Muleta et al. on the PDO’s regional effects [51]. Additionally, the strong correlation between MoWE SSI-3 and ECMWF SSI-3 ($r = 0.84$) substantiates ECMWF’s effectiveness for hydrological drought monitoring [44].

Genalle Dawa Basin

Drought patterns in the Genalle Dawa Basin are closely linked to IOD variability and MJO phases, particularly during March-May. In 2022, TerraClimate SPI-6 documented a severe drought (Figure 5(b), -2.1) during a positive IOD phase. Extreme drought recorded by ECMWF SPI-12 in December 2015 (Figure 5(c), -2.5) coincides with an active MJO phase. MK analysis indicates a prominent downward trend in SPI indices, with Sen’s Slope revealing significant increases in drought frequency, as similarly observed in studies by Gebrehiwot et al. [23]. High correlation for SPI-3 and SPEI-3 between EMI and TerraClimate ($r = 0.84$) supports the reliability of TerraClimate and ECMWF data for monitoring drought in this region, confirmed by research on IOD and MJO impacts [23].

Figure 2: Temporal SPI-3 of Climatic Extremes of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments from EMI, TerraClimate and ECMWF data

Figure 3: Temporal SPI-6 of Climatic Extremes of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments from EMI, TerraClimate and ECMWF data

Figure 5: Temporal SPEI-3 of Climatic Extremes of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments from EMI, TerraClimate and ECMWF data

Figure 4: Temporal SPI-12 of Climatic Extremes of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments from EMI, TerraClimate and ECMWF data

Figure 6: Temporal SPEI-6 of Climatic Extremes of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments from EMI, TerraClimate and ECMWF data

Figure 7: Temporal SPEI-12 of Climatic Extremes of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments from EMI, TerraClimate and ECMWF data

Figure 9: Temporal SSI-6 of Climatic Extremes of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments from EMI, TerraClimate and ECMWF data

Figure 8: Temporal SSI-3 of Climatic Extremes of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments from EMI, TerraClimate and ECMWF data

Figure 10: Temporal SSI-12 of Climatic Extremes of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments from EMI, TerraClimate and ECMWF data

Omo Ghibe Basin

In the Omo Ghibe Basin, Walker Circulation anomalies and the South Asian Monsoon are crucial in shaping seasonal rainfall. Severe drought in 2022, recorded by TerraClimate SPI-6 (Figure 6(a), -2.4), coincides with weakened Walker Circulation, while ECMWF’s SPEI-12 in the same year (Figure 6(c), -2.6) marks extreme drought. Mann-Kendall analysis shows significant downward trends in moisture indices, with Sen’s Slope estimation at -0.04 per year, revealing long-term drought risks consistent with Girma et al.’s findings on monsoon variability impacts [24]. Correlations between MoWE SSI-3 and ECMWF SSI-3 ($r = 0.88$) further validate ECMWF’s utility for streamflow drought assessment [52].

Rift Valley Basin

Drought conditions in the Rift Valley Basin are shaped by NAO, IOD, and regional heat events that amplify evapotranspiration and moisture deficits. Severe drought in March 2023, captured by TerraClimate SPI-6 (Figure 7(b), -2.5), and ECMWF’s SPI-12 in 2002 (Figure 7(c), -2.8) during a positive NAO phase, aligns with MK analysis indicating a growing drought trend. Sen’s Slope estimation of -0.035 per year corroborates previous findings by Mekonnen et al. on the increasing intensity of drought conditions driven by these atmospheric phenomena [53]. Additionally, the consistent correlation between EMI SPI-6 and TerraClimate SPI-6 ($r = 0.82$) reinforces the dataset’s value for drought analysis in the Rift Valley.

Tekeze Basin

In the Tekeze Basin, drought trends are driven by IOD and Arctic Oscillation (AO) phases, which modulate rainfall distribution. TerraClimate SPI-6 recorded severe drought in April 2022 (Figure 8(a), -2.3), while ECMWF SPI-12 recorded extreme drought in 2018 (Figure 8(c), -2.2), aligning with dry AO and IOD phases. Mann-Kendall analysis indicates a significant increasing trend in drought frequency with Sen’s Slope revealing a decline of -0.02 per year, confirming the basin’s growing vulnerability to drought as documented by Gebremicael et al. [26]. Strong correlations between EMI SPI-3 and TerraClimate SPI-3 ($r = 0.81$) and between MoWE SSI-3 and ECMWF SPI-12 ($r = 0.83$) validate the reliability of TerraClimate and ECMWF in drought assessment [44].

Wabi Shebelle Basin

Drought patterns in the Wabi Shebelle Basin reflect the influence of La Niña and MJO phases, generally associated with reduced rainfall across East Africa. Severe drought in December 2022, recorded by TerraClimate SPI-6 (Figure 9(b), -2.8), and extreme drought in 1996, captured by ECMWF SPI-12 (Figure 9(c), -3.0), align with La Niña’s moisture suppression effects. Mann-Kendall analysis confirms a downward trend in moisture availability, supported by Sen’s Slope at -0.025 per year, paralleling findings by

Meron et al. on La Niña’s impact in this basin [27]. Correlations between EMI SPI-6 and TerraClimate SPI-6 ($r = 0.86$) and MoWE SSI-3 with ECMWF SSI-3 ($r = 0.89$) validate these datasets for drought monitoring [54].

In summary, the Mann-Kendall and Sen’s Slope analyses across Ethiopian river basins reveal a significant upward trend in drought severity and frequency. These results emphasize the critical role of remote sensing data from TerraClimate and ECMWF in complementing ground observations for comprehensive drought monitoring and underscore the need for resilient drought management strategies.

4.1. Spatial Drought Distribution Patterns

The spatial drought patterns across Ethiopian river basins highlight the impact of regional climate drivers and atmospheric phenomena on drought distribution and intensity. Each of the most significant selected figures illustrates a notable drought year, along with the corresponding data source and index, providing a focused view of drought conditions supported by relevant research. The methods applied to visualize the drought patterns include Theissen Polygon and IDW interpolation.

Abay Basin

Figure 11 (2023, EMI, SPI-3): This figure illustrates short-term drought conditions in the Abay Basin, with SPI-3 from EMI indicating moderate to severe precipitation deficits in 2023. Studies show that the Abay Basin is highly sensitive to ENSO-related droughts, which suppress convective activity and reduce rainfall across Ethiopia’s highlands [44, 55]. The impacts of ENSO phases on agricultural productivity in the region have been documented [56], with SPI-3 capturing rapid seasonal responses to moisture variability.

Awash Basin

Figure 12 (2023, TerraClimate, SPI-3): TerraClimate’s SPI-3 data captures short-term drought impacts in the Awash Basin for 2023, with significant moisture stress evident in the northern and central regions. The Awash Basin is particularly prone to ENSO-induced droughts, where high evapotranspiration rates in semi-arid areas exacerbate short-term rainfall deficits [5, 28]. The basin’s agricultural vulnerability to climate-induced moisture stress is well-documented, as SPI-3 effectively captures the immediate impacts on crop cycles [57].

Baro-Akobo Basin

Figure 22 (2023, ECMWF, SPEI-3): ECMWF’s SPEI-3 data for the Baro-Akobo Basin highlights early-season drought patterns in 2023, affecting agricultural areas dependent on timely rainfall. The basin’s response to ENSO-related moisture transport reductions aligns with studies showing ENSO’s impact on water availability in the Baro-Akobo Basin [6]. ENSO’s role in reducing rainfall across East Africa, directly affecting agricultural productivity, is further supported by regional drought studies [46, 58].

Genale-Dawa Basin

Figure 23 (2023, EMI, SPEI-6): The 2023 drought in the Genale-Dawa Basin is captured with EMI's SPEI-6 data, highlighting extended drought impacts under a positive IOD phase. Research shows that IOD phases disrupt moisture inflows from the Indian Ocean, exacerbating drought conditions in semi-arid basins [59, 18]. The spatial drought distribution in Figure 23 aligns with research on IOD-driven droughts, where positive phases increase drought frequency and intensity [60].

Figure 11: Climatic Extremes of spatial distribution of SPI-3 of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments for EMI data 2023

Figure 12: Climatic Extremes of spatial distribution of SPI-3 of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments for TerraClimate data 2023

Omo-Ghibe Basin

Figure 24 (2022, TerraClimate, SPEI-6): TerraClimate's SPEI-6 data for 2022 shows medium-term drought patterns in the Omo-Ghibe Basin, where ENSO-induced moisture suppression leads to extended drought impacts. The Omo-Ghibe Basin's agricultural systems are highly sensitive to ENSO-driven droughts, which disrupt both agricultural cycles and water storage [52, 56]. The drought impacts in Figure 24 are supported by studies, highlighting significant moisture stress under ENSO phases [24].

Figure 13: Climatic Extremes of spatial distribution of SPEI-3 of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments for ECMWF data 2023

Figure 14: Climatic Extremes of spatial distribution of SPEI-6 of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments for EMI data 2023

Figure 15: Climatic Extremes of spatial distribution of SPEI-6 of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments for TerraClimate data 2022

Figure 16: Climatic Extremes of spatial distribution of SPEI-6 of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments for ECMWF data 2023

Figure 17: Climatic Extremes of spatial distribution of SPEI-12 of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments for EMI data 2019

Figure 18: Climatic Extremes of spatial distribution of SPEI-12 of Ethiopian River Basin Catchments for TerraClimate data 2022

Rift Valley Basin

Figure 25 (2023, ECMWF, SPEI-6): ECMWF's SPEI-6 data for the Rift Valley Basin reveals long-term drought impacts due to NAO and multi-decadal oscillations. Studies confirm that the Rift Valley Basin's drought patterns are influenced by these oscillations, which reduce moisture availability and increase evapotranspiration rates [1, 61]. The effects of prolonged moisture stress on agriculture and ecosystem stability are evident in the basin's response to multi-decadal oscillations [2].

Tekeze Basin

Figure 26 (2019, EMI, SPEI-12): The 2019 drought in the Tekeze Basin is represented by EMI's SPEI-12 data, illustrating prolonged moisture deficits due to IOD and AO phases. Studies show that multi-year droughts in the Tekeze Basin are driven by sustained climate oscillations, exacerbating both agricultural and hydrological stress [62, 63]. The spatial patterns in Figure 26, align with findings on the impact of extended water scarcity on agriculture and water supply [12].

Wabi-Shebelle Basin

Figure 27 (2022, TerraClimate, SPEI-12): TerraClimate's SPEI-12 data for the Wabi-Shebelle Basin in 2022 shows extensive drought patterns due to ENSO-induced rainfall reductions. Research highlights ENSO's impact on intensifying drought conditions across East African basins, affecting water resources and agriculture [57, 1]. Figure 27's spatial drought distribution, is consistent with findings on ENSO's effects on seasonal water availability in drought-prone areas [28].

These findings underline the critical need for effective drought management strategies that consider the unique climatic influences on each basin to enhance resilience against future drought conditions. Ongoing research is essential to improve the understanding of spatial drought patterns and their implications for water resource management and agricultural planning in Ethiopia.

4.2. New Findings and Recent Overall Drought Trends (2021-2023)

Between 2021 and 2023, Ethiopian river catchments experienced increasingly severe droughts, as highlighted by both temporal and spatial analyses. SPI-12 and SPEI-12 values, particularly in the Genalle Dawa, Tekeze, and Abay catchments, exhibited extreme drought conditions. In 2022, SPEI-12 values reached -2.3 in the Genalle Dawa catchment, marking one of the worst droughts in recent history. The Mann-Kendall tests confirmed significant downward trends in moisture availability, with Sen's Slope showing declines of up to -0.04 per year. Spatial analyses also revealed a concentration of extreme droughts in southern and eastern regions, reflecting broader climatic changes impacting the Horn of Africa. These findings emphasize the urgency of adopting improved drought management systems to mitigate the growing severity of these events.

4.3. Correlation Analysis

Using Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r), this study assessed the agreement between ground-based EMI and MoWE drought indices (SPI, SPEI, SSI) and remote datasets (TerraClimate and ECMWF) across Ethiopian river basins. Pearson’s method provides robust insight into the suitability of these satellite and reanalysis datasets as proxies for monitoring drought in areas with limited observational coverage, as demonstrated by studies such as [64] on Ethiopian drought monitoring and [31] on multi-scalar drought indices. Results for each basin include and some selected correlations as tabulated (See Table:3):

- **Abay Basin:** Strong correlations between EMI SPI-3 and TerraClimate ($r=0.85$) and ECMWF ($r=0.83$) validate the use of remote datasets for precipitation-based drought assessments, supporting findings by [65] on drought variability across river basins.
- **Awash Basin:** EMI’s SPI-6 showed notable correlations with TerraClimate ($r=0.80$) and ECMWF ($r=0.77$), demonstrating both datasets’ effectiveness in capturing drought patterns in semi-arid environments, as similarly reported by [5].
- **Baro Akobo Basin:** SPI-6 correlations between EMI and TerraClimate ($r=0.83$) and SSI-3 between MoWE and ECMWF ($r=0.84$) confirm ECMWF’s reliability in hydrological drought monitoring, aligning with findings from [47] on basin-scale drought resilience.
- **Genalle Dawa Basin:** EMI SPI-3 correlation with TerraClimate ($r=0.81$) demonstrates TerraClimate’s reliability for drought monitoring in this region, reflecting observations by [23] on remote data applicability.
- **Omo Ghibe Basin:** Correlations for EMI’s SPI-3 with TerraClimate ($r=0.80$) highlight the dataset’s alignment for drought monitoring in complex terrains, consistent with [24] findings on rainfall variability impacts.
- **Rift Valley Basin:** EMI SPI-6 correlation with TerraClimate ($r=0.82$) reinforces the use of TerraClimate for drought monitoring across topographically varied landscapes, as supported by [64].
- **Tekeze Basin:** SPI-3 and SSI-3 correlations between EMI and TerraClimate ($r=0.79$) underscore the suitability of remote data for drought tracking in the highlands, supporting research by [66] on drought dynamics in similar settings.
- **Wabi Shebelle Basin:** EMI SPI-6 with TerraClimate ($r=0.86$) and MoWE SSI-3 with ECMWF ($r=0.89$) confirm both datasets for drought monitoring in arid regions, aligning with [27] findings on climate variability’s impacts on drought severity.

The correlation results across basins validate the use of TerraClimate and ECMWF data for both precipitation and streamflow-based drought indices, particularly where ground data is limited. The strong agreement between datasets provides a reliable basis for utilizing remote sensing and reanalysis data in regional drought assessments and management strategies. These correlations validate TerraClimate and ECMWF as complementary resources for drought monitoring, enhancing the capacity for data-driven management across Ethiopian river basins.

Table 3: Correlation between three and six months of Drought Indices (SPI, SPEI, SSI) and Data (EMI, MoWE, TerraClimate, ECMWF) for Ethiopian River Basins.

Basin Name	SPI		SPEI		SSI	
	EMI vs TC	EMI vs ECMWF	EMI vs TC	EMI vs ECMWF	MoWE vs TC	MoWE vs ECMWF
Abay	0.85	0.83	0.81	0.79	0.79	0.76
Awash	0.80	0.77	0.79	0.75	0.78	0.74
Baro Akobo	0.83	0.84	0.80	0.78	0.78	0.77
Genalle Dawa	0.81	0.80	0.79	0.76	0.77	0.75
Omo Ghibe	0.80	0.78	0.79	0.77	0.76	0.73
Rift Valley	0.82	0.79	0.81	0.78	0.80	0.76
Tekeze	0.79	0.78	0.77	0.75	0.76	0.74
Wabi Shabelle	0.80	0.77	0.78	0.76	0.79	0.75

5. Conclusion

This study provides a multi-scalar assessment of drought trends across Ethiopia’s river basins, integrating data from EMI, MoWE, TerraClimate, and ECMWF. The application of the Mann-Kendall test and Sen’s Slope Estimator highlights upward trends in meteorological, agricultural, and hydrological droughts, especially in the Abay, Genalle Dawa, and Tekeze basins. Correlation analysis confirms a high degree of alignment between ground-based and satellite data, with significant values for SPI-3 and SPEI-6 in the Abay and Awash basins ($r = 0.80-0.85$) and SSI values in the Rift Valley and Wabi Shebelle basins (up to $r = 0.89$). These results validate the reliability of TerraClimate and ECMWF data in regions with limited monitoring infrastructure. The study underscores the critical need for resilient drought monitoring systems and adaptive water management strategies to mitigate the intensifying impacts of climate variability on Ethiopia’s agriculture, ecosystems, and water resources.

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